

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Itineraries focused on the narration of specific contents to given target audience

Demo of the web app for the Lower Aosta Valley

SPOKE N 3 – Tourism and culture industry

DELIVERABLE 2.3 UNIVDA - flagship project TOEP

Version history

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Glossary

Definition	
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. Introduction

This report aims to document the work carried out as part of the TOEP Flagship Project aiming to enhance and consolidate the identity of the Lower Aosta Valley (Bassa Valle, BV), through a strategic repositioning that makes it an attractive, authentic and innovative tourist destination, thanks to the digital fruition of its historical, cultural, folkloristic and landscape heritage. The cultural identity of the BV, fundamental both for the local population and for the tourist experience, has been redefined in recent years, progressively abandoning an industrial connotation to embrace a more touristic one. In order to guarantee a distinctive and sustainable positioning, it becomes essential to adopt an integrated approach of cultural resources with new technologies, with a view to digital innovation.

The implementation of a digital system for access and interaction with the historical-cultural and landscape heritage of the territory is proposed, made possible thanks to the development of a cloud platform, usable on smartphones and mobile devices in an immediate and intuitive way. This system allows visitors to access information content that is always available, creating a simplified and immersive experience capable of enriching interaction with the local context. A distinctive element of the model proposed here is the active collaboration with local stakeholders, such as administrations, cultural bodies, tourist guides and territorial associations, who contribute to selecting and defining the points of interest that are most representative of the BV. This participatory approach, also inspired by the principles of *participatory place branding*, guarantees an authentic representation of the identity peculiarities of the territory, offering visitors an experience consistent with the local reality. Each point of interest will be equipped with an information sign with a QR code, which will allow access to a rich variety of digital content through a web application. These e-contents range from classic information sheets to forms of multimedia storytelling that include mythological narratives and historical anecdotes.

The proposed platform collects and systematizes a set of thematic itineraries, which were previously developed by the different researchers involved in the project, each one with different expertise, thus adopting a different point of view. These materials, rich in historical, cultural, linguistic, and natural content, represent a valuable resource for understanding and experiencing the territory.

Our starting point was this pre-existing heritage: a solid but heterogeneous foundation made up of texts, maps, bibliographic references, and thematic insights. From the very beginning, the main need that emerged was to transform these contents into accessible and engaging routes, capable of speaking not only to the academic or scientific community, but also to citizens, tourists, students, territory enthusiasts, and curious explorers.

Our goal was therefore to develop a mode of access that would be clear, intuitive, and at the same time respectful of the original materials complexity. The guiding idea was to design a system that could highlight the uniqueness of each itinerary while maintaining coherence in the overall structure, navigation, and user experience.

In parallel, the platform has been designed to include two additional key components:

- A survey and presentation of local events, connected to the territory and the themes of the itineraries, which can prove relevant when integrating the itineraries themselves, offering concrete opportunities for exploration and participation;
- A particular focus on sustainability, understood both as care for the environment and as the enhancement of soft mobility practices and the role of sustainable local communities, which may serve as key elements for activating, maintaining, and interpreting the routes.

This report is organized to guide the reader through all phases of the work: from the definition of the initial objectives to the actual implementation of the thematic sections, concluding with an overview of the general navigation architecture of the designed system.

2. Technologies used

The development of the digital platform is currently in a prototyping phase, with the goal of testing flexible and scalable solutions for organizing and displaying content related to itineraries, events, and sustainability.

For this initial stage, WordPress¹ was chosen as the development environment. It is a widely used Content Management System (CMS) known for its ease of use, extensibility through plugins, and suitability even in non-technical contexts.

The decision to use WordPress was based on several key advantages:

- Accessibility and ease of use for non-expert users;
- Ability to manage diverse content within a single platform;
- A rich ecosystem of extensions that allows for rapid testing of custom features;
- Support for responsive design, ensuring usability across devices.

In the current prototyping context, a selection of essential plugins has been integrated to explore content representation and management solutions:

- **Leaflet Map:** used to insert and display interactive maps that help geolocate the itineraries across the territory;
- **File Upload Types by WPForms:** it enables the upload of file formats not natively supported by WordPress, such as .gpx files, which are used to represent geographical track data for routes;
- **Raw HTML:** it allows the insertion of custom HTML code within pages or content, offering greater flexibility in structuring and presenting elements
- **Simple Custom CSS & JS:** used to add custom CSS code to solve layout issues such as z-index conflicts, improving the display of overlapping elements on the site

The combined use of these tools has made it possible to establish an effective working base for testing content logic and designing the platform's information architecture.

3. Platform contents

The content represents the core of the platform and serves as element through which the connection between territory, research, and user experience takes shape. At this stage of the project, three main content types have been identified: thematic itineraries, events, and sustainability of touristic facilities.

¹ <https://wordpress.org/>

Each of these entities has been designed to be easily accessible, semantically structured, and visually effective, in order to provide a comprehensive, engaging, and coherent user experience aligned with the goals of the project.

The content is not conceived as static information, but rather as connective elements that enable users to navigate between places, stories, activities, and territorial data, creating personalized and meaningful paths. Their implementation is based on specific informational models capable of integrating text, pictures, interactive maps, geographic tracks, and cross-linked entities.

The following sections describe the key features of each content type, with a focus on the structure adopted for the prototyping phase.

3.1. Itineraries

The page dedicated to each itinerary is structured to offer a complete, narrative, and interactive experience of the route. The goal is to allow users to explore, visualize, and follow the itinerary independently and in depth.

Itinerary Overview

The first section displayed on each itinerary page is dedicated to the overview of the route. This introductory space is designed to provide users with an immediate understanding of the general characteristics of the itinerary, even before exploring the interactive map or the detailed step-by-step description.

Each overview describes the geographic area covered by the route, the type of itinerary, its difficulty, estimated duration, the most suitable seasons for visiting, and practical suggestions such as the recommended mode of travel and possible nearby visits.

The tone and focus of the overview vary depending on the type of itinerary:

- **Olive cultivation and naturalistic routes** highlight the scenic diversity, immersive experience, and the alternation of paved and dirt paths;
- **Toponymic and hiking routes** emphasize the physical aspects of the path, such as elevation, sun exposure, and optional route variants;

- **Historical-literary routes** focus on cultural context, references to authors and works, and all-season accessibility;
- **Industrial archaeology routes** introduce users to the area's industrial past and its evolution, drawing attention to the relationship between landscape and working memory.

The overview serves as the narrative entry point to the itinerary, helping users immediately understand the nature of the proposed experience, the required level of effort, and the cultural or environmental value of the route.

Interactive Map and Route Data

Immediately following the itinerary overview, the page features an interactive map displaying the complete GPX track of the route. This map allows users to visually explore the path in its entirety, with a clear representation of the terrain and the shape of the itinerary.

Along the track, several markers indicate the presence of key points of interest. These are placed precisely on the map and guide the user's attention toward significant locations encountered along the way.

The picture below shows an example of the map with the GPX track and markers visible, before any point of interest is selected.

Figure 1 – Interactive map with GPX track and markers for points of interest

When a user clicks on one of the markers, a pop-up opens displaying the number and name of the corresponding point of interest. This serves primarily as a visual reference along the route, while the full details of each point will be explored later in the expandable sections further down the page.

The next picture shows what the map looks like when a marker is expanded, with its associated pop-up content visible.

Figure 2 - Point of interest marker expanded with visible title and number

To the right of the map, a compact and easy-to-read table summarizes the key characteristics of the route, including total length, estimated duration, difficulty level, elevation gain, recommended mode of travel (on foot, by bike, with e-bike), and the best seasons for completing the itinerary. This information helps users evaluate the route's characteristics and whether it fits their interests or physical condition.

Below the statistics table, a download button allows users to obtain the GPX file of the route. The file can be used on personal devices or GPS navigation apps, enabling independent use of the route during the actual excursion.

Access Information and Route Description

Just below the map and statistics section, users can access an expandable text box that provides practical information on how to reach the starting municipality of the itinerary. This includes

directions by car or public transportation, and may also include tips on parking or nearby facilities. The expandable format keeps the interface clean, while still making useful travel information easily accessible when needed.

Immediately after this, the page presents a detailed description of the route. This section guides the user step by step along the path, including indications of streets, trail intersections, changes in terrain, and turning points. The writing is designed to accompany the user both during planning and in the field.

Whenever the route reaches a point of interest, the reference number of that point is shown in parentheses — for example (4) — making it easier to connect the narrative to the map and to the corresponding expanded content later in the page.

Points of Interest & Insights

Below the route description, the page includes an expandable section that lists all the points of interest encountered along the itinerary. Each point is presented in a collapsible format, allowing users to open only the content they are interested in, keeping the page clean and easy to navigate.

The picture below shows the general layout of this section, where each point of interest is listed by its number and name. At the end of the list, a separate expandable block titled "Approfondimenti" (Insights) is also present. This final section is used to present thematic content that is relevant to the itinerary as a whole but not tied to any specific point on the map.

▼ Punti di Interesse & Approfondimenti

- ▶ 1: Outre l'Ève
- ▶ 2: Lè Pòrtè
- ▶ 3: Ourty
- ▶ 4: Lago di Vercoche
- ▶ 5: Laris
- ▶ 6: Praz Rion
- ▶ 7: Chardonney
- ▶ 8: Li Ban
- ▶ **Approfondimenti**

Figure 3 - Overview of the expandable list of points of interest and thematic insights

When expanded, each point displays:

- The name of the site, shown as the title of the expandable element;
- A photo of the location, when available;
- The place where the site is located;
- A short description highlighting the site's main characteristic;
- A detailed explanatory paragraph;
- When available, an optional in-depth section for users who want to explore the topic further.

Within the descriptions, there may also be hyperlinks to bibliographic references. These allow users to directly access the sources cited, ensuring clarity and transparency while encouraging further exploration.

▼ 1: Outre l'Ève

Località: Champorcher

Caratteristica principale: Borgo rurale con rascard e forno comunitario, snodo storico tra Valle d'Aosta e Piemonte

Outre l'Ève ("letteralmente "oltre l'acqua") è un grazioso villaggio nel quale è possibile notare due rascard in legno e un forno comunitario. La religiosità popolare è testimoniata da numerose croci in legno fissate alle porte (una tradizione comune a tutta la Valle) e dalla cappella che si incontra all'inizio del paese, significativamente affrescata da un pittore Canavesano (Sogno, Forcellini & Petey 1997: 25).

Dal villaggio partiva infatti un'ampia mulattiera, tutt'ora ben conservata, che garantiva i collegamenti con la Val Soana e con la Val Chiusella (e attraverso queste con la pianura piemontese). Troviamo tracce dei commerci con il Piemonte almeno a partire dal XIV secolo (Baudin 1999: 64), secolo al quale risalgono le prime dispute di cui siamo a conoscenza per il possesso dei pascoli d'alta quota. Questi ultimi erano infatti sfruttati anche dalle mandrie provenienti dal Canavese (Baudin & Squinabol 2006: 33), dove durante l'inverno scendevano anche gli animali che non era possibile nutrire a Champorcher.

Figure 4 – Example of a point of interest without in-depth content

▼ 1: Il borgo e il Forte di Bard

Località: Bard

Caratteristica principale: Borgo fortificato con edifici storici e l'imponente Forte di Bard

L'itinerario inizia attraversando il ponte pedonale sulla Dora Baltea e, dopo la SS 26, si entra nel cuore del borgo medievale di Bard, uno dei meglio conservati della Valle d'Aosta. Questo piccolo villaggio fortificato si sviluppa lungo un'unica strada centrale, fiancheggiata da antiche caseforti e palazzi nobiliari risalenti al XV-XVIII secolo.

A dominare il borgo dall'alto è il maestoso Forte di Bard, una delle più imponenti strutture militari alpine. La fortezza, riedificata dai Savoia nel XIX secolo sulle rovine di un'antica fortificazione medievale, oggi ospita mostre, eventi culturali e il Museo delle Alpi.

▼ Approfondimento "Il forte di Bard"

Sin dal Neolitico la Valle d'Aosta è stata terra di passaggio di mercanti, popoli, pellegrini, personalità illustri ed eserciti che hanno profondamente influenzato le vicende storiche, economiche e militari della regione. Il Forte di Bard rappresenta una preziosa testimonianza del sistema di controllo militare, politico e giurisdizionale. Sorge infatti in posizione strategica su un promontorio roccioso sulla sinistra orografica della Dora Baltea, in un punto in cui la valle si restringe a formare una gola, vincolando il transito ai piedi della rocca. Posizione dominante e percorso obbligato hanno reso il sito un punto chiave di osservazione e controllo fin dall'antichità: già all'inizio del VI secolo esisteva a Bard una guarnigione di 60 uomini posti a presidio del luogo (Cortelazzo 2017). Durante il Medioevo i signori di Bard, una delle famiglie nobili più influenti della regione, costruirono una prima struttura difensiva sul promontorio, successivamente ampliata e rafforzata. Nel secolo XI la chiesa di Bard si trasforma da luogo di frontiera a punto di riscossione di pedaggio sulla direttrice del San Bernardo e il castello diventa il centro dell'ascesa della signoria feudale dei Bard, conti locali che accettano l'inquadramento sabauda (Rivolino 2002). Nel 1242, con Amedeo IV, il forte passa sotto il controllo diretto dei Savoia, che ampliano e rafforzano la struttura. Il forte assunse un ruolo chiave nelle difese sabaude, diventando un baluardo contro l'esercito francese nel 1704 e l'arrivo di Napoleone Bonaparte nel 1800. Quest'ultimo, riuscito a conquistare il forte con l'astuzia, ne ordinò la distruzione sistematica sia per il dispetto causato dalla resistenza di Bard sia per considerazioni di ordine politico e strategico. Nel 1830 Carlo Felice di Savoia decise di ricostruire il forte. I lavori si protrassero fino al 1838 e vennero diretti dall'ingegnere militare Francesco Antonio Olivero, che la rese una delle fortezze più moderne e massicce dell'epoca (Devoti 2018). Il nuovo forte era composto da una serie di edifici su diversi livelli, con tre principali corpi di difesa: l'Opera Ferdinando in basso, l'Opera Vittorio nella zona intermedia e l'Opera Carlo Alberto in posizione più elevata, corredata di una piazza interna. Tra la fine dell'Ottocento e l'inizio del Novecento il forte cade in declino, fino alla completa smilitarizzazione avvenuta nel 1975 (Minola 2012). Nel 1990 il forte diventa di proprietà della Regione Autonoma Valle d'Aosta, che avvia un progetto di recupero edilizio e riconversione in polo culturale di rilievo. Il progetto ha previsto la realizzazione del Museo delle Alpi, inaugurato il 15 gennaio 2006. Il museo, sviluppato in 30 stanze, guida il visitatore nel racconto dei diversi temi legati alla montagna, articolati in quattro parti: il paesaggio alpino, la conoscenza delle Alpi tra natura e cultura, la civiltà alpina e la trasformazione verso la modernità (Giacobini 2007).

Figure 5 – Example of point of interest with additional in-depth insights

The final "Approfondimenti" section offers users the opportunity to dive deeper into broader topics related to the itinerary's theme, such as linguistic aspects, historical context, environmental features, or cultural heritage. This structure allows thematic information to be clearly separated from localized content, providing flexibility in how users engage with the material.

Bibliography

At the end of the page, a dedicated bibliography section lists all the sources referenced throughout the itinerary. These may include books, academic articles, archive materials, official websites, and other documents used in the creation of the content.

The references are presented in a clear and consistent format, making it easy for users to identify the origin of each citation. Throughout the itinerary page, especially in the descriptive and in-depth section, hyperlinks are used to connect specific mentions directly to the corresponding bibliographic entry.

This approach ensures full transparency, supports academic and educational use of the itineraries, enhancing their reliability and traceability.

3.2. Events

Another key content element of the platform is the section dedicated to events. These are local events taking place across the lower Aosta Valley and are often thematically linked to the itineraries, enriching the user experience and promoting active engagement with the territory.

At the top of the section, an interactive map displays all current and upcoming events, using markers positioned on the municipalities involved. When clicked, each marker opens a pop-up containing essential information about the event, including:

- The period of the year when the event takes place;
- The type of activity (such as excursions, workshops, tastings, and more).

This allows users to quickly identify which events are happening, where, and when.

Mappa degli eventi:

Figure 6 – Interactive map with event markers pop-up showing event details

Below the map, users can explore events through three expandable text blocks, each offering a different way to organize the content:

- The first section presents events grouped by municipality, allowing users to browse what's happening in each town or village.

Panoramica degli eventi

Figure 7 – View of the expandable section for browsing events by municipality

- The second section organizes events by month, making it easy to plan visits around specific timeframes.

Panoramica degli eventi

▶ Eventi per Comune

▼ Eventi per Mese

▶ Gennaio

▶ Febbraio

▶ Maggio

▶ Giugno

▶ Luglio

▶ Agosto

▶ Settembre

▶ Ottobre

▶ Novembre

Figure 8 – View of the expandable section for browsing events by month

- The third section filters events by category offering a thematic filter. The categories available are visible in Figura 9

▼ Eventi per Tipologia

▶ Cultura e Tradizioni

▶ Enogastronomia e Artigianato

▶ Sport e Natura

▶ Spettacoli ed Esperienze Sensoriali

▶ Eventi Didattici e Familiari

Figure 9 – View of the expandable section for browsing events by category

Each event listed within these expandable sections includes a title, photo, period, location, and a brief description.

This allows users to explore events both geographically and thematically, enhancing their understanding of the local cultural fabric and offering concrete opportunities to experience the places and traditions connected to the itineraries.

3.3. Sustainability

The final core content area of the platform is sustainability. In a region like the lower Aosta Valley, where natural landscapes and traditional communities are tightly interwoven, promoting sustainable practices is essential to preserve both the environment and local culture.

The sustainability section introduces users to a mindful way of experiencing the territory. It encourages actions such as traveling by foot or bike, respecting natural trails and protected species, and choosing environmentally friendly accommodations and services. Special attention is also given to the use of renewable energy, water resource management, and the promotion of local and zero-kilometre products.

This content is not just informative, but also an invitation: users are encouraged to explore the region responsibly, discover local producers, and support slow mobility to reduce their environmental impact while deepening their connection with the landscape.

In future developments, this section will include an expandable area with advanced insights. Users will be able to access interactive visualizations, statistics, and infographics related to sustainability indicators, tourism impact, and resource use in the region.

4. Navigation Architecture

The final section of this report outlines the navigation architecture of the platform, designed to offer a smooth, intuitive, and informative experience for users of all types.

The entry point is the home page, which functions as a hub providing quick access to the platform's main features. Its layout is simple and content-oriented, with the following key elements:

- Shortcut to the interactive itinerary map: prominently placed on the homepage, this shortcut allows users to immediately explore all available itineraries through a dynamic and geolocated interface.

- Overview statistics: a small section summarizes essential data, such as the number of itineraries available and the number of municipalities involved.
- Itinerary categories description: a brief explanation of the different types of itineraries available (e.g., historical-literary, industrial archaeology, olive cultivation, and toponymic-hiking).
- About us section: a concise introduction to the people and institutions behind the project, accompanied by a button that links directly to the full About page.

In addition to the homepage, the platform features a persistent top navigation bar that includes a section for itineraries. This menu opens into a dropdown submenu offering different access points to the content

4.1. General Itinerary Map

The first option in the "Itineraries" submenu is the general itinerary map. This interactive map provides a geolocated overview of all the routes available on the platform.

Each itinerary is represented by a marker placed at its starting point. When a user clicks on a marker, a pop-up window opens, displaying two columns:

- On the left side, a preview picture representing the itinerary's landscape or theme
- On the right side, the title of the itinerary, which is clickable and redirects to the full itinerary page

Below the title, the pop-up also shows a set of essential statistics, such as:

- Total length;
- Estimated duration;
- Difficulty level;
- Suggested travel mode (e.g. on foot, by bike).

In addition to the markers, the entire GPX track of each itinerary is displayed on the map. Each route is colored according to its category, matching the marker color:

- **Green** for toponymic-hiking itineraries;
- **Red** for olive cultivation itineraries;

- **Black** for industrial archaeology itineraries;
- **Blue** for historical-literary itineraries.

These visual elements allow users not only to locate the starting point of each itinerary but also to understand its full geographical development and thematic context at a glance.

Figure 10 – General Itinerary Map with the legend for each type of itinerary

4.2. Category Itinerary Map

Figure 11 – Categories submenu

Accessible from the "Categories" submenu within the main "Itineraries" section, this page allows users to explore the routes based on their thematic focus. Each thematic group represents a specific way of interpreting and experiencing the territory: whether through historical memory, linguistic heritage, traditional agriculture, or industrial heritage.

Upon selecting a category (e.g., Toponymic-Hiking, Olive Cultivation, Historical-Literary, or Industrial Archaeology), the user is taken to a dedicated map displaying only the itineraries belonging to that group.

As described previously, the map includes the starting point markers and the full GPX tracks, all shown in a single color specific to the

The pop-ups follow the same structure as on the general map, with a preview picture, clickable title, and basic statistics.

Panoramica degli itinerari toponomastici-escursionistici:

- ▶ Arnad e il suo mantello di castagni
- ▶ Lo Tsoëmin di Léngue tra Champdepraz e Issogne
- ▶ L'éva dell'Evançon tra Challand-Saint-Victor e Challand-Saint-Anselme

Figure 12 – Example of category-specific itinerary map

Below the map, an expandable list presents all itineraries in that category. Each entry includes:

- A short overview of the route;
- A “Continue to itinerary” button that links directly to the full itinerary page.

Panoramica degli itinerari toponomastici-escursionistici:

▼ Arnad e il suo mantello di castagni

I periodi migliori per percorrere questo itinerario sono l'autunno, quando i boschi sono più colorati, e la primavera, quando il caldo non è troppo intenso, e gli animali non sono ancora saliti agli alpeggi: l'esposizione del versante garantisce infatti un clima mite per quasi tutto l'anno.

[prosegui all'itinerario](#)

▼ Lo Tsoëmin di Léngue tra Champdepraz e Issogne

Entrambi gli itinerari si svolgono per lo più nel bosco: tuttavia, mentre seguendo quello breve si è sempre esposti a nord, quello lungo attraversa pendii più assolati, con tratti in cui la vegetazione è meno folta. Si tratta dunque di itinerari percorribili tutto l'anno (con l'esclusione dei periodi di innevamento, che richiedono attrezzatura e conoscenze specifiche), che si apprezzano al meglio in primavera, quando i faggi mettono le foglioline nuove, e in autunno, quando i larici sono gialli. Mentre il percorso "breve" è adatto a tutti, quello "lungo" richiede un buon allenamento: pur senza coprire una distanza eccessiva, l'itinerario presenta un importante dislivello, che solo in parte si supera per raggiungere la quota massima: una volta giunti al colle, bisogna infatti contare ancora circa 300 metri di "saliscendi" lungo il sentiero di rientro.

[prosegui all'itinerario](#)

► Léva dell'Evançon tra Challand-Saint-Victor e Challand-Saint-Anselme

Figure 13 – Expandable list of itineraries with preview and direct access

This layout allows users to both explore the map and quickly access any itinerary of interest through the list view.

4.3. Towns Itinerary Map

Figure 14 – Municipalities submenu

The final filtering option in the "Itineraries" section is the "Municipalities" submenu, which allows users to explore all routes that start in or pass through a specific town in the lower Aosta Valley.

Each municipality page displays a map showing the starting point markers for all related itineraries and the full GPX tracks, each colored according to its category.

The pop-ups are identical to those used in the general itinerary map and category map.

Below the map, users find expandable text sections grouped by category. Only the categories that have at least one itinerary in the selected municipality will be shown.

Within each category block, every itinerary is presented as in category map.

Panoramica degli itinerari di Pont-Saint-Martin:

- ▶ Itinerari Olivicoltura
- ▶ Itinerari Archeologia Industriale

Figure 15 – Pont-Saint-Martin itineraries

The main navigation bar also includes dedicated sections for Sustainability and Events, allowing users to access these content areas directly from anywhere on the platform.

In future developments, these sections may be further integrated into the itinerary pages themselves.

This planned integration would enhance the coherence of the platform, connecting experiences, places, and values in a seamless user journey.

5. Conclusion

A project aiming at enhancing the BV's identity represents an innovative and sustainable approach to the promotion of cultural heritage, with the aim of creating responsible and inclusive tourism. The key words – digitalization of cultural heritage, web platform, participatory place-branding – summarize the essence of this initiative, which aims to strengthen the identity of the BV and guarantee a unique and authentic experience for visitors. In this sense, the platform represents a virtuous example of how digital technologies can be used not only to facilitate access to services and the organization of tourist flows, but also to create experiential paths that lead the visitor to discover and appreciate local realities. Its use is thus transformed into a journey to discover a territory that, through this digital infrastructure, becomes accessible and enhanced in all its most genuine components. The expected results include the promotion of responsible and sustainable tourism, the enhancement of the unique identity of the BV and the possibility for visitors to live a memorable and genuine experience. Thanks to the integration of multimedia content and interactive storytelling, the platform offers discovery paths that respect the environment and support the local economy. This model is an example of how digitalization can become a tool at the service of cultural tourism, maintaining a balance between accessibility and integrity of the heritage.

The implementation of a system of this type presents some challenges. The need for adequate digital infrastructures, potentially lacking in some areas of the territory, could compromise the accessibility of the system for residents and visitors. Furthermore, a limited representation of some categories of local actors could generate partial or not very inclusive narratives. Furthermore, creating digital content that is captivating and respectful of local cultural specificities, avoiding stereotypes or trivializations is a challenge. Even the maintenance and updating of the system, which require economic resources and specific skills, could represent an obstacle for a territory still in a phase of economic transition.

Looking at possible future developments, it is crucial to continue collecting and rationalizing thematic itineraries, to organize cultural resources in a structured and easily usable way. The further development of the proposed prototype of the web platform will be crucial to test and optimize the interaction of visitors with the BV heritage, while validation in the territory will allow to collect direct feedback from communities and tourists, ensuring a solution that truly responds to local and tourist needs.